

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING
JIZZAX FILIALI

**ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION
TADQIQOTLARNING
DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI
VA RIVOJLANISH
TENDENSIYALARI:
YECHIMLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR
RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI
TO'PLAMI**

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**MIRZO ULUG‘BEK NOMIDAGI O‘ZBEKISTON MILLIY
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**ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION TADQIQOTLARNING DOLZARB
MUAMMOLARI VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: YECHIMLAR
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EDUCATIONAL MULTIMEDIA IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS OF ENGLISH

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Summary: This paper focuses on how advanced educational multimedia can enhance the vocabulary acquisition of young learners in English classroom. The analysis shows that a wide range of multimedia used by teachers at successive stages of vocabulary acquisition makes linguistic material more comprehensible through visual, audio, and situational supports as well as contributes to a reliable transfer of vocabulary from short-term to long-term memory.

Key words: English as a foreign language; young learners; vocabulary acquisition; multimedia.

Foreign language teaching methods offer a wide range of methods and techniques for working with vocabulary. The effectiveness of mastering vocabulary depends on the correct organization of work at all stages: from the initial presentation of a word to its automation and development into free speech. An important aspect preceding the selection of specific teaching methods is the selection of vocabulary and the form of its initial presentation. Modern linguodidactics emphasizes the need to shift the focus from memorizing isolated words to the acquisition of lexical units, or lexical chunks, as vocabulary in natural speech functions not as a set of individual units, but in the form of set phrases and collocations [4]. For young learners, this means that it is more appropriate to introduce new words in the context of phrases that are typical for them. For example, instead of studying the verb *play* in isolation, it is more productive to initially present entire structures: *play football* or *play the piano*. It is also important to pay close attention to word frequency. At the initial stage of learning a new language, the bulk of vocabulary should include high-frequency words, which form the core of the language and cover the vast majority of everyday communication situations.

The organization of work with the selected lexical minimum should be based on the principle of deep and comprehensive study, which I. Nation defines as “rich

instruction”. This approach involves targeted pedagogical influence on all aspects of word acquisition: “its phonetic and graphic form, conceptual meaning and grammatical functions” [5]. At the primary school stage, intensive learning requires the teacher to use multi-channel methods of semantization. Within this approach, an additional aspect that determines the choice of working methods is the concept of learning burden of a lexical unit which is the amount of cognitive effort required to acquire it [5]. For primary school students, words with international roots (e.g., *doctor, tennis, sport, taxi* etc.) are characterized by a light learning burden, and their semantization takes a minimum of time. On the contrary, words that differ significantly phonetically and conceptually from their native language counterparts require the use of a full range of intensive learning methods.

In teaching vocabulary to young learners, non-translation methods using various visual means of semantization are more preferable compared to direct translation. These techniques can include the use of static graphic images (pictures, photographs, cards), as well as dynamic representation of the lexical units (gifs, video fragments, short cartoons); demonstration of actions (facial expressions, gestures, pantomime); demonstration of real objects. The use of real objects is crucial for young learners, as they think in concrete terms. The physical contact with an object helps create a strong neural connection between it and its foreign-language name. Graphic visualization allows for the presentation of vocabulary quickly and effectively, avoiding the use of the native language, which facilitates the creation of a direct conceptual bridge between the image and the English word.

The semantization stage is followed by the consolidation and memorization of lexical units. Here, various cognitive and mnemonic strategies come to the fore – from traditional word cards with pictures to the spaced repetition combined with retrieval practice which allow vocabulary to be transferred from short-term memory to long-term memory. Transforming receptive vocabulary knowledge into productive knowledge requires proper planning of the training phase. Semantization and initial reinforcement alone are not enough to develop a stable vocabulary skill. The methodological model must include a mandatory vocabulary recycling system. S. Thornbury formulates this principle as “use it or lose it”, indicating the need for regular involvement of previously learned words in new speech situations and combining them with new grammatical material [6].

In recent decades, teaching methods have shifted toward the active use of multimedia technologies. Research has shown that students who learn vocabulary through audiovisual formats demonstrate significantly higher word retention compared to those who learn vocabulary from traditional text materials [1]. Multimedia resources enable “dual encoding”, where information reaches the brain simultaneously through visual and auditory channels.

In modern scientific and pedagogical literature, the concept of multimedia does not have a single, universal interpretation, which is due to the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon. Z. Zhang notes that “multimedia integrates text, graphics, animation, audio and video, providing students with colossal amounts of information and stimulating their imagination and creativity” [7]. However, for pedagogy, the cognitive and didactic meaning of this term is more significant. R. Mayer, the founder of the

cognitive theory of multimedia learning, defines multimedia as “a form of presenting material using both words (printed or audio) and images (static illustrations or dynamic animations and videos)” [3]. According to his concept, multimedia learning is the process of constructing mental representations based on words and images, which allows for a deeper understanding of the material compared to traditional monomodal (text-only) learning. A. V. Dikov offers a detailed classification of modern multimedia web tools, grouping them by the type of information sources created and their functional purpose. Based on this classification, we can identify the following main types of multimedia resources and characterize their specific didactic features:

- text and hypertext environments (blogosphere and Wiki systems);
- tools for visualizing meanings and concepts (services for generating word clouds, creating mind maps, and developing infographics);
- resources for digital storytelling (services for creating slideshows, educational comics, animated videos, and digital books);
- means for visualizing spatiotemporal connections (services for generating timelines and interactive stories on geographic maps);
- video-oriented interactive environments (for transforming passive viewing into active cognitive activity);
- digital environments for collaborative visual work (online whiteboards as an efficient tool for brainstorming and collaborative projects) [2].

The integration of multimedia technologies into teaching vocabulary to young learners means not simply a change in the information carrier (from paper to digital), but a fundamental restructuring of the didactic system. In a general pedagogical context, the use of multimedia contributes to the implementation of a student-centered approach, individualization and differentiation of learning. The relevance of multimedia in language learning is based on the distribution of cognitive load between the visual and auditory channels. If semantization of lexical units is given only in text, through translation or non-translation techniques, the visual channel is overloaded. If text is replaced by a voice explanation combined with dynamic animation, both channels are engaged, which significantly improves the quality of information absorption and reduces the effect of cognitive overload. It is particularly important in teaching young learners because the level of their reading skill development is not high and this can negatively influence the understanding and memorizing words in a new language. Multimedia enriches the context, making linguistic and factual material more comprehensible through visual, audio, and situational supports.

The use of interactive multimedia in foreign language teaching has a solid theoretical foundation. The introduction of multimedia helps reduce the “affective filter” (in the terms of S. Krashen’s hypothesis), creating a psychologically comfortable and safe environment, which is critical for primary school students. Interactive computer systems provide students with modified language input and immediate, personalized feedback, which are fundamental conditions for successful second language acquisition. Multimedia applications play a specific and indispensable role in the development of vocabulary skills. The process of vocabulary acquisition through digital media is based on the principles of multimodality: a new lexical unit is presented to the learner simultaneously in graphic, auditory, and visual (pictogram, illustration)

forms. This directly correlates with the cognitive theory of multimedia learning, according to which parallel processing of information across visual and auditory channels leads to deeper cognitive understanding and reduced working memory overload. Furthermore, digital applications allow for the algorithmic implementation of a spaced repetition system and implement gamified control, which ensures a reliable transfer of vocabulary from short-term memory to long-term memory. For young learners, game mechanics and interactive formats are the leading means of maintaining concentration and sustaining intrinsic motivation to learn a foreign language.

To sum up, it should be noted that multimedia technologies possess high didactic potential at all stages of vocabulary acquisition:

- at the semantization stage, they ensure instant imprinting of the graphic and auditory image of a word through interactive visualization (double-sided digital cards, images, gifs and videos);

- at the practice stage, interactive crosswords and simulators automate spelling and combinatorial skills, providing students with immediate feedback and reducing academic anxiety through gamification;

- at the speech production stage, multimedia serves for the construction of quasi-communicative situations where vocabulary serves as a natural tool for problem solving.

Thus, methodologically sound integration of multimedia resources into teaching English to young learners supports the transformation of the routine process of foreign language vocabulary acquisition into a personally meaningful, interactive, and highly effective cognitive activity.

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